

IFAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
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MILESTONE REPORT

Recommendations of RI-INNOV Coordination Group

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ABSTRACT

A RI Co-Innovation Platform has been set up and implemented by the “Advanced Communities” of RIs addressed in the Horizon 2020 call INFRAINNOV-04-2020. It is coordinated by an RI Open Innovation Coordination Group (RI-INNOV CG). The group has performed joint support actions to foster the innovation potential in European RIs. The general goals of the coordination group have been cooperation on innovation related actions, exchange of information and jointly strengthening collaboration with industry.

The regular in-depth exchange between the projects I.FAST, AIDAInnova and LEAPS-INNOV has led to joint initiatives and workshops to present the actions and outcomes regularly throughout the project duration of the three projects. Additionally, feedback on these actions has been provided jointly to EC. A final recommendation of the coordination group is to keep the lively exchange between the communities active beyond the project duration through the LEAPS, TIARA and AIDA communities.

IFAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

A RI Co-Innovation Platform has been set up and implemented by the “Advanced Communities” of RIs addressed in the Horizon 2020 call INFRAINNOV-04-2020. It is coordinated by an RI Open Innovation Coordination Group (RI-INNOV CG). The group has performed joint support actions to foster the innovation potential in European RIs. The general goals of the coordination group have been cooperation on innovation related actions, exchange of information and jointly strengthening collaboration with industry.

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2. Overview of the Exchange Platform

- **Objectives:** The “Advanced Communities” of RIs addressed in the call INFRAINNOV-04-2020 agreed to implement an RI Co-Innovation Platform. In order to exploit synergies, coordinate activities, and share results among the selected innovation pilots (light source technologies, accelerator technologies, and detector technologies for accelerators) the coordination group has addressed the following proposed objectives:

(i) to define a common approach for the scientific areas that are at the boundaries between the competences of the different communities,

(ii) to exchange information on the advancement and results of the respective projects,

(iii) to identify areas of cooperation and, where appropriate, to launch common initiatives in the form of workshops, studies, joint position papers, etc. Possible areas of cooperation cover technology transfer, models and schemes for cooperation with industry, standardisation of equipment, training, etc.

The “RI Innovation Knowledge and Technology Transfer Network” (RI-INNOV KTT network exchanges on knowledge and technology transfer models exploited by the various innovation pilots.

- **Structure and Participants:**

To facilitate an effective exchange, an RI Open Innovation Coordination Group (RI-INNOV CG) and a RI-INNOV KTT network have been formed:

- RI-INNOV CG (Coordination group):

The RI-INNOV-CG is coordinated by the three project coordinators. Its members are the scientific coordinator and her/his deputy and one other representative. At its first meeting, the group has nominated a chair being in charge of organising the meetings. The chair is rotated on a regular basis between the communities.

Additional project members such as the WP leaders of the “industry-relation” work packages, organisers of the BSBF activities, or the ATTRACT coordinator have been invited on need.

- RI-INNOV KTT network:

A joint “RI Innovation Knowledge and Technology Transfer (KTT) Network” of knowledge- and technology transfer experts from partners of the successful projects of INFRAINNOV-04-2020 has been part of the RI Co-Innovation Platform. It is managed on work package level, i.e. in LEAPS-INNOV by WP8.

- **Implementation:**

- RI-INNOV CG

At the beginning of the projects, the members have signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU, see appendix), defined joint activities and clarified possible collaboration with the other projects, e.g. ATTRACT (INFRAINNOV-03-2020). The RI-INNOV CG meets at least twice a year, as agreed in the MoU.

Regular exchange every 2-3 months of the coordination group has been realized throughout the project duration. The complete list of 21 meetings from October 2019 to December 2024 is available at <https://indico.cern.ch/category/16380/>, with access to the agenda and accompanying material for each meeting.

- RI-INNOV KTT network

The aim is to exchange experience and best practice on collaboration with industry and support the RI-INNOV CG in implementing joint activities in field of KT/TT. Dedicated meetings at least once a year and exchange at appropriate events such as the biennial Big Science Business Forum (BSBF) have regularly been organized throughout the duration of the projects.

3. Key Achievements and Impact

- **Scientific, Technological and Innovation Actions of RI-INNOV Coordination Group:**
The INFRA-INNOV pilots coordination group has stimulated exchange on innovation amongst the advanced communities of research infrastructures.
 - Presentation of the planned and ongoing actions and outcomes of all pilots at the respective annual meetings in 2022 and 2023.
 - Several online workshops on Intellectual Property Rights management, organized by LEAPS-INNOV, webinar open to AIDA and iFAST, invitation circulated
 - Presentations of actions and outcomes at BSBF 2022, Granada and BSBF2024, Trieste
 - Common presentation for the TIPP2023 Conference, Cape Town, South Africa, Sept 4-8, 2023: P. Giacomelli presentation on behalf of INFRA-INNOV at the Knowledge & Technology Transfer session at the TIPP23 conference: <https://indico.tlabs.ac.za/event/112/overview>. Title “Co-developments with industries within large EU funded infrastructural projects
 - Presentation at 85th ESFRI Forum, Tenerife, Spain (José Manuel Pérez, TIARA), Sept 28-29, 2023
 - Joint Industry Workshop on “Cryogenics in Big Science”, April 16-17, 2024
 - Common booth and presentations of pilot outcomes at BSBF 2024, Triest, Italy, Oct. 1-4, 2024

Impressions from BSBF 2024

- INFRA-INNOV COORDINATION – DG/RTD A4, Brussels July 13, 2023
- Innovation Pilots Workshop with ATTRACT, Oct 14, 2024
- **Scientific, Technological and Innovation Actions of KTT Network:**
 - Meet-up in person at BSBF 2022 on LEAPS booth for those there from ICO and procurement side, Oct. 5, 2022
 - LEAPS-INNOV, I.FAST and AIDAInnova participated in “BIGINN Know and Tech Transfer workshop” at HZB Berlin, March 9, 2023

Impressions from BIGINN Know and Tech Transfer workshop

HZB, Berlin 2023

- AIDAInnova Advanced Mechanics Workshop in Valencia, April 27, 2023
- Joint LEAPS ICO meeting in Lund with participation of AIDAInnova and I.FAST, May30 – June 1, 2023

Group Photo, Lund 2023

- Harwell Science Campus, Big Science event with suppliers, Nov. 3, 2023
- ALBA Synchrotron, Industry opportunities in light sources infrastructures, Dec. 1, 2023
- Joint activities at BSBF 2024 showcasing project results, Oct 1-4, 2024
- Anticipate combined meeting LEAPS-INNOV, RITRAIN+. RITIFI, AIDAInnova and I.FAST in spring 2025

- **Impact:**

The joint actions of the RI Co-Innovation Platform have led to significantly improved visibility of the innovation pilots in the RI communities and in the industrial landscape. In-depth presentation of the developed technologies and innovation actions and exchange with industry at a number of events has raised awareness of the opportunities at the involved RIs both, for industry as well as for the involved RIs themselves. This cooperation is now leading to new joint projects and activities.

A rigorous exchange on technologies at the border of the involved fields as well as innovation aspects has benefited the involved scientists and is also leading to combined actions on bringing these technologies forward for all communities. The strategic exchange between the accelerator, detector and lightsource communities benefits the respective roadmapping processes for FP10 as well as lessons learned on how to approach an effective exchange with industry. Finally, structured exchange with the European Commission benefits both, the RI communities as well as EC, in efficiently assessing the RI communities' needs.

4. Lessons Learned and Recommendations

- **Lessons learned**

Exchange of the organizational bodies (LEAPS, TIARA, AIDA), joint actions among the communities, towards industry and a joint conversation with EC has already resulted in common activities, strategic exchange in view of FP10 and will be most fruitful long-term. It will improve the conversation between scientists of the involved RI communities as well as identify joint opportunities for technology development, user engagement and working with industry as well as enable discussions about synergies and the identification and definition of the necessary steps for their implementation.

The RI Platform requires a sustainable organization between the communities and voluntary involved in future actions from all three communities. An organization team for the exchange between the communities is required long-term and needs to be based within the consortia of the respective communities, i.e. LEAPS, TIARA and AIDA. Communities could take turn yearly to organize and chair the platform.

- **Recommendations**

The RI-INNOV coordination group recommends to keep the RI Platform active beyond the duration of the innovation pilots which will end in September 2025. An active RI platform allows for a better and faster exchange and therefore a higher strategic impact within and beyond their respective communities. However, a meaningful long-term interaction requires funding for joint actions and travel for meetings.

Joint technology developments for technologies relevant for all communities as well as innovation actions can benefit all communities equally. At the same time it also has to be recognized that significant differences exist, for example in many technology areas needed for RI operation (e.g. optics and user instruments for LEAPS), but also aspects such as transnational access and user involvement. Identifying common and differing areas of interest improves shaping of the respective profiles and targeting the most appropriate funding options.

Both, the involved research and technology development communities as well as policy makers like the EC, can benefit from such a structured exchange platform which could also be expanded towards additional RI communities in the future.

The platform's sustainability will most certainly be enhanced by (limited) support from EC. Based on the common experience of the pilot communities, models for long-term support for key technological areas of European Research Infrastructures can and should be identified and developed.

A final recommendation from the INFRA-INNOV group, taking into account all the considerations above, is to organise a coordinated submission to the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-DEV-05 (Preparatory actions exploring future frameworks for research infrastructures investment plans and funding streams, for integrated and sustained scheme for access and for joint technology development) Area 3 (joint technology development).

The submission is organised by the three communities (TIARA, AIDA, LEAPS) that will connect with other “Big Science” communities and with the health and biology scientific domain. Deadline for submission is expected to be 18 September 2025.

The abstract of the submission, as agreed by the INFRA-INNOV communities, is reported here below.

Abstract for an INFRA-INNOV submission to HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-DEV-05

Since more than 10 years, research and innovation communities representing technology developers and users of Research Infrastructures (RIs) have been advancing towards a better internal coordination for a structured definition of the technological needs, user access strategies and internal management of the research infrastructures on their scientific and technological fields. This is specifically the case of the three scientific communities that replied to the Horizon-2020 INFRAINNOV-04-2020 call, within which EC promoted the consolidation of matured communities, targeting in parallel synergetic efforts among different communities.

In the last three years, the light-sources, detectors and accelerator R&D communities, in the frame of their corresponding INFRAINNOV-2020 projects, have given steps towards a better coordination of their activities. The coordination group among LEAPS-INNOV, AIDA-INNOV and IFAST has represented the most efficient forum for the three communities to discuss and share their own technology development plans. But it is still a preliminary approach to an appropriate coordination scheme.

The project COORDINA-INNOV aims at consolidating an internal and transversal coordination scheme of the three consolidated communities described above, following the approach initiated in INFRAINNOV-2020. It is a reply for a definition of a better organization and coordination among the light-sources, detectors and accelerator R&D communities, with links to other related ones. The main objective is to ensure that the necessary technological innovation in the European Research Infrastructures is carried out in a coordinated way, avoiding duplication and in close contact with industry, preparing the ground for the consolidation of a coordinated co-innovation ecosystem.

COORDINA-INNOV focuses at designing a coherent and viable coordination scheme, based on the development of the roadmaps of the three R&D community for deploying their specificity and internal strategies and setting out coordination bodies to homogenize strategies. It will propose a supra-community coordination body to guarantee coherence among the roadmaps and a proper alignment on the strategies of the three communities for technology development for research Infrastructure. The actual level and dimension of the structure for a real useful and practical coordination will be analyzed by the three communities, in a trade-off between communities' internal competences and the global need for a more general coordination scheme.

Under the coordination scheme proposed, we plan to manage:

- The definition of the key and enabling technology building blocks demanded for the upgrading of existing European RIs and the development of the next generation ones, distributed among domain-specific needs, but articulated in a single technological challenges list, classified in accordance with the vision and indications of the industry.
- Coordinating the Education and Training needs for researchers, RI personnel, users and industry.

- Defining a suitable inter-community communication scheme.
- Analyze coordination approaches for the access of users to the RIs.
- Definition of the roles of the different actors essential for the RI technology development needs: RIs, technological infrastructures, industry, universities and research institutions.
- Design the programs for implementing the R&D internal plans, both at low TRL and high TRL. Definition of the funding mechanisms, including industrial-focused R&D funding programs.
- Proposals to set-up of the co-innovation strategic program with industry. Consolidation of the industry representation bodies. Identification of needs and mechanisms to promote the creation of new start-ups or supporting the already initiated ones to properly reply to the actual demand.